

THE IMPORTANCE OF SPIRITUALITY AND NATIONAL IDENTITY IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the importance of understanding our national culture, national identity and spirituality and provides information on its importance in the education system.

“If the body of society is the economy, then the soul is the spirituality. When we decide to build a new Uzbekistan, we will rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is the rich heritage of our ancestors and a strong spirituality based on national values”

Shavkat Mirziyoyev

Today, we live in a period of rapid change, a time of intense and complex change that is radically different from what mankind has ever experienced. Statesmen and politicians, philosophers and sociologists, commentators and journalists describe this period differently and call it by different names. Some call it the age of high technology, some the age of thinking, and still others the age of general information.

Of course, in all of these ideas, there is a sense of truth, of rationality. Because each of them naturally reflects some of the signs of today's diverse and colorful life. But it is also a time of globalization. In many ways, I think this definition accurately reflects the essence

of the problem. It is no secret that no matter what happens on any part of the world today, mankind will immediately find out about it on the other side of the world.

Talking about such a phenomenon of globalization, it should be noted that the term has a very broad meaning today as a scientific, philosophical, vital concept. In general, this absolute means the formation of a new economic, socio-political, natural-biological global environment in a new sense, and at the same time, the existing national and regional problems are becoming global problems.

Speaking about the main factor and the reason why the process of globalization is entering our lives faster and deeper, it must be objectively acknowledged that today the development and prosperity of any country is so closely linked not only with its near and far neighbors, but also with other regions and regions. It is clear that it is not difficult to understand that the exclusion of any country from this process will not lead to positive results.

In this sense, our first President Islam Karimov, realizing that globalization is, first of all, an unprecedented acceleration of the pace of life, it is necessary to take a look at the situation in the spiritual sphere, which is accompanied by positive changes in economic, social and political spheres. High spirituality is an invincible force "was presented to the general public. This work embodies the spiritual history, present and past of our people, and every reader who reads it will feel boundless feelings of love and pride. The work consists of an introduction, an introduction and four chapters, covering all areas of spirituality.

Spirituality is an incomparable force that purifies a person spiritually, encourages him to grow in heart, strengthens his inner world, will, faith and conscience, and is the sum of all the positive qualities of a person.

The author begins by recalling the dark days of the system and society that caused the spiritual poverty of the Uzbek people with a thousand-year history, so that the most spiritual man can not repeat and understand the mistakes of the past today mentioned.

One of the greatest and most valuable achievements of independence has been the realization of national identity. Through our national identity, we have come to understand and apply our spirituality, our values, our history, our traditions, our nation, and our language, our religion.

At the same time, the reality of life shows that any product of progress can be used for two purposes - good and evil. If we look at the history of mankind, the development of its thinking, we can see that there has always been a struggle between good ideas and teachings that call people to perfection and high goals in life, and between evil and harmful ideas. we see that this struggle continues today. In these struggles,

we must understand how spiritual and responsible we are.

Today, the movement in the modern information space is so intense, so fast, that now, as before, yes, this event took place far away from us, and it cannot be ignored that it has nothing to do with us. It is not uncommon for a people or a nation given such a mood to lag behind in development for hundreds of years. We have seen proof of this in the last century.

In a sense, ideological polygons today are more powerful than nuclear ones. The aspect of this issue that always urges one to be vigilant is that if there is military, economic, political pressure, it can be felt, seen, prevented, but it is extremely difficult to quickly grasp the ideological pressure, its effects and consequences. That is why in his works, the President advocates spiritual poverty - an ideological threat. They said that we should oppose it with a strong ideological consciousness.

In such a situation, if a person does not have his own independent opinion, time-tested vital-national values, a sound worldview and a strong will, he will be exposed to all kinds of spiritual threats, both overt and covert. It is difficult to withstand the impact. This can be seen in many of the events that have taken place in daily life, and I don't think there is any need to go into detail about the serious consequences. The events that have taken place in the world and in our region over the past years, which we have experienced directly, and the development of ideological processes, have repeatedly proved that this conclusion is correct.

Today, our young people receive a variety of information and information not only in schools, but also through radio and television, the press, the Internet. In such an environment, where the world information space is expanding, it is necessary to educate

our children not only to read it, but also to see it, to surround them with an iron wall, and, of course, to meet the demands of the times. , does not fit our noble purpose - our intentions either. After all, we have set ourselves the task of building an open and free democratic society in our country, and we will never back down from this path.

Therefore, we envision the future of our state not in our own shells, but in the deepening of universal and democratic values. We see our future in the experience of developed countries, in the liberalization of public administration, in the wider implementation of human rights and freedoms, in the diversity of ideas in our lives. We stand for a peaceful, free and prosperous life, mutually beneficial cooperation with the entire enlightened world and the international community.

That's the decent thing to do, and it should end there.

In short, in order not to create a gap in the spiritual world of our youth, we need to instill in their hearts and minds a healthy lifestyle, respect for national and national values - a sense of respect from childhood.

It should not be forgotten that even a small message against human spirituality today, which at first glance seems insignificant, is a huge loss of power invisible to the naked eye, but its damage can not be compensated by anything that can deliver.

We all know that in order to keep the borders of any state inviolable, military force is as important as water and air. But today it is natural for all of us to think about what we should rely on to preserve the inviolability of the spiritual world of our people, especially the younger generation.

Based on a fact that has been confirmed many times in my life, I would say that we must always be vigilant, vigilant and vigilant in the face of such growing dangers. Such threats can be met with a well-thought-out, well-organized, well-organized, regular, and continuous spiritual education.

It should be clear to all of us that where indifference and indifference prevail, when the most pressing issues are left to selfishness, then spirituality becomes the weakest and most vulnerable point. And, conversely, where vigilance and zeal, high intelligence, and contemplation prevail, spirituality becomes a powerful force.

Also, our current President pays more attention to these values and beliefs. Even, in a meeting, "The ideology of the new Uzbekistan we are creating will be the idea of goodness, humanity and humanism. When we say ideology, we mean, first of all, the education of thought, the education of national and universal values. They are based on the life concepts and values of our people for thousands of years", - said the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

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